

PHARMACOGNOSTICAL STUDY OF *KAPIKACHHU* SEED (*MUCUNA PRURIENS* (L.) DC.) CULTIVATED THROUGH HYDROPONICS - NUTRIENT FILM TECHNIQUE (NFT)

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ABSTRACT

Background - *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) is a well-known medicinal plant in Ayurveda, is extensively used for its therapeutic potential in conditions such as Parkinson's disease, nervous disorders, infertility, and as a rejuvenative tonic. Traditionally, it is cultivated in soil-based systems; however, modern cultivation practices like hydroponics offer an alternative to overcome challenges such as soil-borne diseases, variable yield, and declining arable land. Among hydroponic methods, the Nutrient Film Technique (NFT) provides a continuous flow of nutrient solution to the plant roots, ensuring optimal growth and improved phytochemical profiles. **Materials and Methods** - For the present study, seed wild variety of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) has been selected as herbal drug. A thorough study has been carried out of seed wild variety of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through

Hydroponics - Nutrient Film Technique (NFT). including its macroscopical and microscopical (pharmacognostical) studies. **Observation & Result** - In the present study Pharmacognostical Identification of Seed wild variety of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) was done which included macroscopical, microscopical. The Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Nutrient Film Technique (NFT) is creamish white, oval, smooth in touch and odourless. In the transverse section of the seed, several features were observed, including in TS of Testa Epidermal cell, Bearer cell,

Parenchymatous cell, starch grain and in TS of cotyledon Epidermal cell, Bearer cell, Parenchymatous cell, starch grain and oil globules. **Conclusion:** The structures which are observed here help in correct identification of seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) In this study, *Kapikachhu* Seed (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Nutrient Film Technique (NFT) were found to be (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) botanically compared with standard reference. No new structures were found during microscopy.

KEY WORD: Hydroponics, NFT (Nutrient Film Technique), *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.), Medicinal plants, Cultivation.

INTRODUCTION

The word 'Hydroponics' comes from the Greek term's 'hydro', meaning *water*, and 'ponos', meaning *labor*.^[1] Hydroponics, the method of growing plants without soil by providing nutrients directly through water solutions, has emerged as a viable solution to these challenges. Among the various hydroponic systems, the Nutrient Film Technique (NFT) is widely recognized for its efficiency. In NFT, a thin film of nutrient-rich water flows continuously over the plant roots, ensuring adequate oxygenation and nutrient absorption.^[2] This technique allows better control of the growth environment, enhances phytochemical content, Reduces the risk of soil borne pathogens like (harmful effect of pesticides), and contributes to uniform plant development. For medicinal plants like *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.), such methods may also preserve or even enhance their bioactive constituents, thereby supporting both traditional and modern therapeutic applications.

Kapikachhu (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.), also known as *Atmagupta*, is a revered herb in Ayurveda, traditionally celebrated for its potent aphrodisiac, strength-promoting, and rejuvenating properties. *Kapikachhu* is well-documented in various Ayurvedic texts, with references found across multiple *Samhitas* and *Nighantus*, highlighting its aphrodisiac, rejuvenative, and neurological benefits. Rich in L-DOPA and other bioactive compounds such as tannins, flavonoids, alkaloids, and phenolic compounds.^[2] *Kapikachhu* has been widely used to enhance male fertility, improve testosterone levels, and boost muscular strength and endurance. Known as the "athlete's friend," this herb supports lean muscle development, reduces fat accumulation, and enhances physical performance. Additionally, it has mood-elevating effects and has shown benefits in managing depression and increasing libido. Beyond its aphrodisiac potential, *Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) is pharmacologically significant

in the management of conditions such as Parkinsonism, diabetes mellitus, rheumatoid arthritis, atherosclerosis, menstrual disorders, and tuberculosis.^[3,4] As a legume of the Fabaceae family, it contributes to soil fertility by fixing atmospheric nitrogen. *Kapikachhu* is well-documented across classical Ayurvedic texts, confirming its historical and therapeutic relevance. This review aims to comprehensively examine the Ayurvedic and modern scientific perspectives of *Kapikachhu*, highlighting its multifaceted pharmacological actions and clinical applications.

VERNACULAR NAMES^[5]

Table No. 1: Vernacular Names of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.)

No.	Region	Names
1.	Sanskrit	<i>kapikachhu</i> , <i>Atmagupta</i>
2.	English	Cowitch, Cowhage
3.	Hindi	Kaunch, Kevachh, Kevanch, Khujani
4.	Gujrati	Kancha, Kanchan, Kavatch
5.	Bengali	Akolshi
6.	Punjabi	Kawanch, Gugli
7.	Tamil	Punaippidukkan
8.	Telgu	Pilliadugu
9.	Oriya	Kaincho
10.	Marathi	Kavacha, Kuhili, Kanchkun
11.	Urdu	Kavacha

TAXONOMICAL DESCRIPTION

Table No. 2: Taxonomical classification of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.).

Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Angiospermae
Class	Dicotyledoneae
Order	Fabales
Family	Fabaceae
Subfamily	Faboideae
Genus	<i>Mucuna</i>
Species	<i>Pruriens</i>
Binomial Name	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i> (L.) DC.

AIM

To perform macroscopical, macroscopical (pharmacognostical) study of seed wild variety of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated through Hydroponics - Nutrient Film Technique (NFT) with a specially designed protocol.

OBJECTIVE

1. To study the macroscopic features of seed wild variety of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Nutrient Film Technique (NFT).
2. To study the microscopic features of seed wild variety of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Nutrient Film Technique (NFT).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Seed Wild variety of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) were Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Nutrient Film Technique (NFT) used as a drug material. A detailed macroscopic and microscopic study of seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) were carried out to establish the correct identity of the seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) by comparing with standard reference book of Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India (API), Part I, Vol. III 6^[6] and Quality Standards of Indian Medicinal Plants (Vol. 1).^[7]

The work plan was as follows:

1. Plant collection and identification
2. Pharmacognosy study
 - A. Macroscopic study
 - B. Microscopic study

1. Plant Collection and Identification

Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) was Collected from from the hydroponic system Nutrient Film Technique (NFT) established at the Medicinal Plant Cultivation and Technique Research Laboratory(MPCTRL), Government Ayurveda College, Vadodara. **Fig. 1: a and Fig. 1: c** After the proper collection The Macroscopic, Microscopic study studies were performed at Pharmacognosy laboratory of Upgraded department of *Dravyaguna Vijnana*, Government Ayurveda College, Vadodara.

2. Pharmacognosy Study

A. Macroscopic Study

The morphological studies were carried out for shape, size, color, odour and surface of the Seed wild variety of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Nutrient Film Technique (NFT).

OBSERVATIONS

Table No. 3: Macroscopic study of Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Nutrient Film Technique (NFT).

No.	Macroscopic Characters	Observation	Figure No.	Reference
1.	Shape and structure	Oval	Fig 1.c	[8]
2.	Colour	Creamish white		
3.	Odour	Odourless		[9]
4.	Touch	Smooth		[10]
5.	Taste	Sweetish-bitter		[11]

Plate No. 1: Photos of Macroscopy of the Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Nutrient Film Technique (NFT).

Fig 1.a Collection of *kapikachhu* seed wild variety from Hydroponic – NFT

Fig 1.b *Kapikachhu* fruit

Fig 1.c *Kapikachhu* seed

B. Microscopic study

The freehand transverse section of the Seed wild variety of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) was taken and slide was prepared separately using reagents Saffranine and Iodine. Various microscopic structures of transverse section (T.S.) of the Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) were evaluated.

B1: Observations of transverse section of the Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.)

Table No. 4: Microscopic study of the Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Nutrient Film Technique (NFT).

No.	Types	Characteristics of Seed of <i>Kapikachhu</i> (<i>Mucuna pruriens</i> (L.) DC.)	Figure no.
1.	TS of	Epidermal cell	Fig 2.a

2.	testa	Bearer cell	Fig 2.b
3.		Parenchymatous cell	Fig 2.c
4.		Starch grain	Fig 2.d
5.	TS of cotyledon	Epidermal cell	Fig 2.f
6.		Parenchyma	Fig 2.e
7.		Starch grain	Fig 2.g
8.		Oil globules	Fig 2.g, Fig 2.h

late No. 2: Photos of Microscopy of the Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) ultivated Through Hydroponics - Nutrient Film Technique (NFT).

(A) T.S. of Testa

B) T.S. of Cotyledon

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Kapikachhu (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) is an important plant which is used in many diseases mentioned in Ayurvedic system of Medicine literature.

In the present study Pharmacognostical identification of Seed wild variety of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Nutrient Film Technique (NFT) was done which included macroscopical, microscopical features of the same.

The Seed of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Nutrient Film Technique (NFT) is creamish white in colour, oval, smooth in touch and odourless. In the transverse section of the seed, several features were observed, including in TS of testa Epidermal cell, Bearer cell, Parenchyma cell, starch grain and in TS of cotyledon Epidermal cell, Bearer cell, Parenchyma cell, starch grain and oil globules.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the pharmacognostic characterization of the of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.) Cultivated Through Hydroponics - Nutrient Film Technique (NFT) sample confirms. The identify of the plant as a *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.). In this study macroscopic characters oval Shape and structure, creamish white, odourless, smooth in touch, Sweetish-bitter in taste were found and in microscopic characters including in TS of testa Epidermal cell, Bearer cell, Parenchymatous cell, starch grain and in TS of cotyledon Epidermal cell, Bearer cell, Parenchymatous cell, starch grain and oil globules were found so, this given seed wild variety of *kapikachhu* correct identify of the plant as a *kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.). No new structure found rather than standard reference given for identify of *Kapikachhu* (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC.).

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